

ETHNOMEDICINAL STUDY OF UREH NAN AMPEK AND SICAREK PLANTS THAT USED BY PANDAI SIKEK SOCIETY : A REVIEW

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Minangkabau Land, West Sumatera are province in Indonesia that have high biodiversity especially in plant biodiversity. Plant provide a variety of ecosystem services, including medicine, food, repellent, and have long history that been used by local society to meet their daily needs (Diaz-Jose et.al, 2019). Some of plant are endemic and some of them were often used by community and even have their vern name known by the society. Pandai Sikek is a part of the Tanah Datar Regency and this regency considered by Minangkabau history as an oldest regency in West Sumatera (Isnanda et.al, 2015). As an oldest regency in West Sumatera especially in Minangkabau people history, the society has culture in using plant as traditional medicine. Unfortunately, there has been no research on ethnomedical studies of plants used by the Pandai Sikek community. So far, some areas that have been used as place of ethnomedicine research in West Sumatera are Pasaman, Mentawai, Padang, and Pesisir Selatan regency (Putri, 2022). Pandai Sikek can be used as a new place for this research and another medicinal studies such as clinical test for the plant used by communities as traditional plant. Also several research of ethnomedicine are focused in famili taxa of the plant species, but not cross-taxa that have advantage in multi-ranged species approach (Nurainas et.al, 2021). This research can be a novel research, aside from the new place and new approach value, but also new data that can be collected in this area.

Several interview data from people in Pandai Sikek and field survey at March 14, 2024 was collected together with KKN Tematik activities. Some plant that used as traditional medicine such as Ureh nan Ampek, Sicarek, Kamumu, Kundua, Dulang-Dulang and Kambuik-Kambuik. Until now, there is no research about clinical trials for Ureh nan Ampek and Sicarek extract. Kamumu, Kundua, Dulang-Dulang and Kambuik-Kambuik are plants that used by Minangkabau society that already proved by scientific research and clinical trials. For the example Kamumu (*Colocasia esculenta*) sap are used by society to treat wounds, and research Nurhayati et.al (2022) proved the Kamumu extract effective towards wound healing. Kambuik-Kambuik or *Physalis angulata* have used as antidiabetic by society of Minangkabau. And the extract of Kambuik-Kambuik have high antiinflammatory and antinociceptic (Nogueira et.al 2013; and Santo, 2021). Last but not least Kundua or *Benincasa hirsuta* were proven have high antioxidant and high in Vitamin C (Kabra et.al, 2013; and Patty et.al, 2021). All this plant then identified by their scientific name and literature review was conducted. This data can be assessed and executed as cornerstone for medicinal research (clinical test) from this traditional plant extract and can lead into significance data and research in the future.

Previous research has shown studies of plants in West Sumatera more focuses on ethnobotany which has a wider range. It includes another aspect than medicine such as crafts,

natural pesticide and spices (Tribudiarti et.al, 2018). As example research by Suwardi et.al. (2023) ethnobotany of wild edible fruits in Pesisir Selatan has found many utilization by the society. It including food, construction materials, fuel wood and fodder. In the other hand, ethnomedicinal study offer research gaps in the form of potential clinical trials of several plant extracts, that local people believe are effective for certain disease. Studies by Nurainas et. al, (2021) showed new approach that also discussed most part of the plant that used for medicine. This new method can be applied for cross-taxa ethnomedicine in another places in West Sumatera such as Pandai Sikek. According to, Arifin et.al, (2019) Minangkabau communities using Ureh nan Ampek to treats fever. Ureh nan Ampek is a general conception for Minangkabau society in medicinal plants consist of Sitawa (antidote), Sidingin (neutralizer), Cikarau (defender) and Kumpai (destroyer). One of the Ureh nan Ampek is Sitawa or *Costus speciosa*. This plant comes from Zingiberaceae family and according to Selim & Al-Jaouni (2016) this plant have high anti-inflammatory in 50 µg/mL dosage and reduced TNF- α (an inflammatory factor) . By this research, Sitawa could be effective towards fever, as we know fever is one of the symptoms of inflammation due to heatiness. But there is no paper or research that study Sitawa extract towards actual fever-disease model in rat (in-vivo study). Aqueous extract of Sitawa also high in antioxidant (vitamin C) and have high scavenging activity towards free radicals up to 78% by using DPPH method. This study further strengthens the evidence of research gap regarding clinical trials of Sitawa extract against fever, cause Vitamin C is important as curative agents in fever. This antioxidant activity by Sitawa were proven have antiulcer and anticholesterol (Sediwah et.al, 2019; Kujur et.al, 2019).

Another plant that part of Ureh nan Ampek is Sidingin or *Kalanchoe pinnata*. It also used to treat fever and one of the research conducted by Nascimento et.al (2017) found Sidingin high of quercetin. Quercetin is one of the substances that high in antioxidant. Even though aqueous extract of sidingin contains quercetin and proven have antiinflammatory effects that inhibit TNF- α in cancer but still there is no research about effects of Sidingin extracts towards fever (Ferreira et.al, 2014). This proven that the research gap about Ureh nan Ampek extracts towards fever have big opportunity to be conducted as ethnomedicinal research topics. Kumpai or *Panicum maximum* one of the another plant from Ureh nan Ampek that act as destroyer also does not have any research towards fever. In fact, other paper research by Udobang et.al, (2020) Kumpai have high anti-inflammatory effects that reduce inflammation caused by edema and allergies in mice. Last but not least of Ureh nan Ampek, Cikarau or *Enhydra fluctuans* that proven have high in flavonoid that can act as anti-inflammatory (Sannigrahi et.al, 2011). Same with kumpai, the extracts were tested and effective in reducing pain and reducing inflammation by edema in mice (Roy et.al, 2021) But unfortunately, research about Ureh nan Ampek towards fever still not attract many researcher to prove their effects towards fever. From Ureh nan Ampek we move to another plants that used by Pandai Sikek society as medicinal plant, one of them is Sicarek. Sicarek are famous because it is written in the one of the famous poem of Minangkabau culture.

Sicarek or *Clausena excavata* used by Minang communities to treats several disease such as wounds, malaria, headache, fever, abdominal pain caused by dysentery, diarrhea,

tuberculosis, cold, snake bites and food poisoning (Albaayit et.al, 2020). Research conducted by Albaayit and Maharjan (2022) Sicarek extracts showed retard the progression of acute and chronic inflammatory and induce immune cells. From this research, even though it was proved have high anti-inflammatory, but still there are so many research gap such as clinical test of this extracts towards specific disease. Inflammatory-related disease that can be used for research such as this extract towards malaria, dysentery, diarrhea, tuberculosis, snake bites and even food poisoning is needed to be tested and researched (Majdalawieh & Fayyad, 2015). Conclusion of this review are Ureh nan Ampek and Sicarek extract is needed to be explored and proved their ethnomedicine potential. Because Sicarek and neither Ureh nan Ampek still not have any publication and research towards their ethnomedicine potential in clinical tests or in-vivo study.

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